

THE NEED AND REQUIREMENTS DRIVING THE DEVELOPMENT OF POLYMER COMPOSITES FOR AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATIONS

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SUMMARY: This presentation will provide an overview of the need, requirements, and constraints governing the development and application of polymer composites in automotive structures. It will discuss the efforts underway by the Automotive Composites Consortium, a joint R&D partnership among Chrysler, Ford, and General Motors, to lead the technology developments required for the cost-effective application of these new materials in mass-produced vehicles.

KEY WORDS: automotive composites, composites development requirements, automotive composites consortium, automotive polymer composites, fiberglass reinforced plastics in automotive applications

INTRODUCTION

Energy conservation, environmental protection, and the concomitant enhancement in quality of life are so important to us that much of our human endeavor is focused on these worthy, interrelated objectives. The role that materials technology plays in supporting these objectives is by no means minor, and is especially important in supporting these objectives through improvements in automotive technology. The advances in automotive products and the processes by which they are created, developed, and manufactured are dependent on prerequisite advances in materials and processes that support the automotive industry or those industries related to it. So materials technology paves the pathway for progress in automotive technology.

The need for this progress is intensifying as public awareness of our finite energy and environmental resources creates market, societal, and political pressures for safer, fuel-efficient, environmentally-friendly vehicles at the affordable costs to which we have become accustomed. The Partnership for A New Generation of Vehicles (PNGV) in the United States and other similar joint government-industry initiatives in Asia, Europe, and North America are but a few examples of efforts throughout the industrial world to develop a "Super Car".

The general requirements for this Super Car are that it must be safe, affordable, energy-efficient, environmentally-friendly, durable, and reliable with good quality and the capacity and performance to which we have become accustomed. These requirements can be reduced to two words: "Low Cost"--in the broad sense of the term. For example, a safe vehicle minimizes the cost in terms of human suffering and misery to the individual and community.

It also minimizes the losses to society, or units thereof, incurred due to inconvenience, injury, or death resulting from vehicular mishaps. An affordable vehicle provides reliable transportation at costs that are commensurate with available financial resources allowed for acquisition, operation, and maintenance. Obviously, affordability is an essential prerequisite requirement. Energy-efficiency minimizes the costs to energy resources expended for the development, manufacture, use, and disposal of the vehicle. The costs to the environment during development, manufacture, use, and disposal must also be minimized in order for the vehicle to be considered "environmentally friendly". Finally, the vehicle must provide value in terms of performance to expectations--capacity, quality, durability, and reliability must all minimize hassle, inconvenience, and the negative value concomitant with the cost of poor quality.

Hence these components of cost are but a few examples of those that all combine to comprise the total or full life-cycle cost to all of those finite resources expended to acquire, use, and dispose of the vehicle. This total cost should be counted as a "fully accounted cost" and minimized systemically by optimizing each cost component. Thus, a low-cost vehicle can enhance the quality of life by providing obvious advantages to individuals and society while maintaining good stewardship of our human, energy, and environmental resources.

Among the obvious advantages that automotive vehicles provide are a mobile society with concomitant increase in productivity, trade, and the distribution of wealth. Less obvious is the benefit brought to a society by one of the three high value-adding, wealth-creating enterprises--manufacturing. The manufacturing enterprise includes the creation, design, and development of the product and contributes significantly to the economic vitality of industrialized societies. The other two wealth-creating enterprises, mining and agriculture, also benefit by supporting the fuel needs of vehicles (petroleum "mining") and using vehicles for farm mechanization. When a society can compete in a global economy by enhancing its enterprises that create wealth and help utilize output (vehicles) from such enterprise to move goods for trade--all without the over-utilization of its natural resources--the quality of life is enhanced and long-term economic gains ensue.

Therefore, having an industry which has played such an important role in creating wealth, improving mobility, and enhancing the quality of life in industrial societies, it is very important to support this industry with technologies that will help it contribute to our drive toward better stewardship of our human, energy, and environmental resources.

Foremost among the technologies that are required to support this drive to improve automotive energy-efficiency and environmental-friendliness is materials technology. Innovative materials technology and designs will be required to meet the energy-efficiency goals of the Super Car. To meet these goals, it is estimated that a 50% reduction in the weight of both body and chassis will be required.

Several materials are current candidates that are expected to contribute to these aggressive weight reduction targets. Alloys of aluminum, magnesium, titanium, and iron high-strength steels in innovative designs, metal-matrix composites, ceramics, engineering plastics, and polymer composites are among them. Polymer composites have been among the leading candidates for years as materials for weight reduction in automotive body and chassis applications. The requirements and constraints for these composites will be outlined in this presentation. Both business and technical barriers will be addressed, along with the concomitant constraints of costs and cycle time which are so crucial to successful application

of composite materials technology in the automotive industry. These automotive requirements will be presented in the light of realistic business, engineering, and manufacturing constraints in hope that the composites R&D community will help address these needs in the context of the constraints and conditions outlined.

THE NEED FOR POLYMER COMPOSITES

As indicated earlier, polymer composites are engineering materials that hold high potential to:

- Reduce Vehicle Weight
 - Reduce Energy Consumption
 - Reduce Impact on the Environment
 - Reduce Dependence on Imported Fuel
 - Reduce Trade Deficit
- Reduce Tooling Investment Cost
 - Reduce Manufacturing Complexity
 - Reduce Break-Even Volume

The weight reduction potential is an attractive asset because of the need to improve the energy efficiency of the vehicle without sacrificing capacity or performance. The Partnership for a New General of Vehicles (PNGV) has set a mass reduction target of 50% for both body and chassis systems and an overall weight reduction of 40% in order to make its 80 mile/gallon stretch goal a realistic probability. This PNGV fuel economy goal is third among the three PNGV goals. All three PNGV goals are:

1. **Manufacturing:** Reduce manufacturing costs and product development times for all car and truck production.
2. **Near-Term Advances:** Pursue advances that increase fuel efficiency and reduce emissions of standard vehicles.
3. **Breakthrough Vehicle:** Super Car - Develop a new class of vehicles with up to 3 times the fuel efficiency of today's comparable vehicles.

The elements of goal three include:

- Triple Current Fuel Economy (80 mpg)
- Intrepid / Lumina / Taurus Size, Performance, and Cost
- Meet Current and Anticipated Safety Standards
- Improved Recyclability and Reduced Vehicle Emissions
- Concept Vehicle by 2000 and Production Prototype by 2004

This third goal is the most visible of the three PNGV goals and is often dubbed the Super Car. Other vehicle objectives include:

- 5-Passenger Capacity
- 0-60 mph in 12 Seconds
- 90 mph Top Speed
- 200 Mile Range
- Maintenance Free for 100,000 Miles
- Equivalent to Today's Full Size Cars

While progress in the development of polymer composite for automotive applications can be expected to lend support to each of these three goals as the technology evolves, it is unrealistic, however, to expect fiberglass-reinforced polymer composites alone to provide the weight reduction required to achieve the targeted fuel efficiency. Therefore, other materials and innovative designs are expected to be employed.

Among the other materials is the closely-related but more expensive cousin--carbon-fiber reinforced polymer composites. Whereas this material has high potential for reaching the weight-reduction target, it is currently priced far beyond the cost target imposed by the automotive market. Efforts are currently underway to provide carbon fiber at much less than the familiar \$12/lb. Prices at an attractive \$3 to \$5/lb. are far more economically appropriate for automotive applications.

THE ISSUE OF COST

The high-volume, mass production of low margin products is a very cost-sensitive enterprise. Capital investment manufacturing process and material costs must be optimized to maximize value to the customer. The quality and performance-to-price ratio must be maximized in order to compete in a value-sensitive and very competitive market. Therefore, material and manufacturing cost must always be kept in mind and minimized where it can be done without reducing quality and value.

The following simple calculations illustrate the small (\$3,055) margin of cost increase a value-conscious customer might be willing to pay for a "Super Car" at current fuel prices if he or she were to govern the purchase decision simply by personal economics--attributing little or no value to environmental quality.

If fuel costs for traveling 100,000 miles in a 5-passenger car at 27 miles/gallon were 3,704 gallons x \$1.23/gallon = \$4,555; and in a 5-passenger car at 82 miles/gallon were 1,220 gallons x \$1.23/gallon = \$1,500--the difference in fuel costs would be \$3,055 (plus environmental costs).

The next scenario shows a larger margin (\$8,571) available for additional vehicle cost at fuel prices of \$3.45/gallon. If fuel costs for traveling 100,000 miles in a 5-passenger car at 27 miles/gallon were 3,704 gallons x \$3.45/gallon = \$12,778; and in a 5-passenger car at 82 miles/gallon were 1,220 gallons x \$3.45/gallon = \$4,207--the difference in fuel costs would be \$8,571 (plus environmental, economic, and political costs).

The results of these simple calculations must be considered when determining the additional costs available for materials or any other technology incorporated into a Super Car in various fuel-price markets. Many customers, however, would be willing to spend more than the break-even with fuel cost in order to contribute to the societal goals of improving environmental quality. Nevertheless, cost is in most cases the bottom line.

REQUIREMENTS FOR AUTOMOTIVE COMPOSITES

The requirements and constraints imposed on automotive composites are captured by the three Rs of our industry:

- Rapid
 - High Volume Manufacturing
 - Automated

- Robust
 - Operate in a "Non-Ideal" Plant Environment
- Reasonable Cost

A "generic" list of automotive composites requirements shows:

- Low Materials Cost
- Short Cycle Time
- Robust Processing Window
- Fast, Reliable Assembly/Joining Technology
- Long Durability in Automotive Environments
- Reliable and Acceptable Crash Energy Management
- Minimal Environmental Impact
- Energy-Efficient Manufacturing
- Customer Acceptance
- High Performance-to-Weight Ratio

These requirements, although not specific, are indicative of the material requirements of the industry. There are also other needs, such as:

- Need for Low-Cost High-Modulus Fibers
- Fiber Size Developments
 - Capability for Rapid Processing (Chopping?)
 - Compatibility with low-Cost Fast-Cure Resins
- High Temperature Property Retention (>120°C)
- Long-Term Durability and Damage Tolerance
- Crash Energy Management Characteristics
- Economically Viable Recycling

In addition to the cost constraints discussed earlier, there are dominant constraints for all advanced materials. Among them are:

- Customer Acceptance (Internal Customers)
- Market Acceptance (External Customers)
- Economic Issues
- Environmental Issues (at Low and High Production Volumes)

There are also concerns that are derived from the aforementioned. These are challenges that must be overcome whenever new materials/processes/design technologies invade a long-established methodological culture.

Common Composites Concerns

- Implementation Strategies
- Design, Materials Processing, and Applications Match
- Material Supply and Processing Issues
- Development Costs and Funding
- Capital (Investment) Costs
- Manufacturing (Molding, Assembly, Coating)

- Materials Characterization and Inspection Issues
- Customer Acceptance
- Energy, Environmental, and Economic Impact

THE AUTOMOTIVE COMPOSITES CONSORTIUM

The Automotive Composites Consortium, a joint R&D partnership among Chrysler, Ford, and General Motors, was organized to lead the technology developments required for the cost-effective application of these new materials in mass-produced vehicles.

Formed in 1988, the Automotive Composites Consortium (ACC) is progressing well towards its goal of developing the technology of structural polymer composites to accelerate its application in vehicles. In cooperative programs with supplier companies and government laboratories and funding, the ACC is prototyping structural members for vehicles, demonstrating high-volume processing technology, developing design methodology for crash energy management, advancing composite joining techniques, and establishing materials test standards.

Prior to the formation of the ACC, each of the U.S. Big Three automotive companies individually conducted programs that established the performance of prototype composites in structural applications such as front rails, floor pans, side aperture panels, space frames, and crossmembers. However, manufacturing technology to produce large structural parts and vehicles which meet the high production volumes and low costs demanded by the automotive industry was not demonstrated. The ACC is striving to meet automotive productivity and cost goals using glass fiber reinforced thermoset materials made by liquid composite molding (LCM), which includes structural reaction injection molding (SRIM) and resin transfer molding (RTM).

Recently, however, the scope of the ACC has been expanded to include thermoset and thermoplastic structural composite materials manufactured by compression molding in its long-range plan and will be further broadened to include all automotive structural polymer composites, irrespective of the manner in which the composite was formed.

Supplier involvement is critical to the operation and success of the Automotive Composites Consortium. Corporations and government laboratories have participated in ACC programs through cost-sharing arrangements. These organizations share the new technology generated in the cooperative program. In addition, the ACC works with many companies and selected universities on a contractual basis and has recently become a partner with the National Institute of Standards and Technology in the Advanced Technology Program (ATP) for our Focal Project II.

Today, the ACC is an integral part of the United States Automotive Materials Partnership (USAMP), an emerging group of partnerships investigating a wide range of polymeric and metallic materials that can be used to maintain high performance levels while reducing vehicle weight. This partnership, including ACC, seeks to support the goals of the Partnership for a New Generation of Vehicles (PNGV) and the high-priority national "Super Car" initiative, which will also be briefly discussed. All of the pre-competitive R&D consortia of Chrysler, Ford, and General Motors operate under the auspices of the United States Council for Automotive Research (USCAR).

This partnership among Chrysler, Ford, and General Motors is proving to be a successful approach to developing structural polymer composites. Aggressive programs to develop and demonstrate new processing methods, design techniques for crash energy management, joining methods, and materials test standards are producing results. The ACC has successfully concluded its first Focal Project and is proceeding with its second application program, Focal Project II, to develop and demonstrate the capability to produce large LCM structures in a cost-effective, robust process.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

- Automotive Applications of Composites are Steadily Evolving
- Auto Industry Recognizes Potential for Structural Polymer Composites
- Future Growth in Automotive Composites Depends on Technological Developments and Market Demands
 - Cost Reduction
 - High-Volume Manufacturing Methods
- PNGV and Future Vehicles Offer Potential for Advanced Composite Materials

In order for the automotive industrial enterprise to continue to pursue its primary purpose, as captured by Chrysler's statement of purpose:

"To Produce Cars and Trucks that People Will Want to Buy,
Will Enjoy Driving, and Will Want to Buy Again",

while also pursuing the implementation of new technologies to meet the needs of the 21st century, we must:

- Learn About Each Other's Needs and Capabilities
- Banish "NIH"
- Promote Government Assistance on R&D to Support Strategic Industrial Initiatives

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